

Nurturing Soft Skills and Emotional Intelligence: A Particularly Asian Perspective

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Accepted 05 April 2024

Keywords:

Asia, assessment, authority, collectivism, communication, context, control, cross-cultural sensitivity, emotional expression, emotional intelligence, hierarchy, historical trauma, indirect communication, individualism, intangible skills, remote learning, resilience, skills development, soft skills

ABSTRACT

This paper interrogates the hegemonic notion that ‘soft skills’ and ‘emotional intelligence’ ensue as universal concepts that can be adequately defined by one set of persons—scholars living in the Global North, for example—then effectively applied *carte blanche* to another set of persons—citizens living in the Global South, for example in this treatise.

To unpack the power dynamics of soft skills and emotional intelligence pedagogies, the author explores a number of specific examples contrasting Asian perspectives which collectively shine a light on broader patterns of marginalization and intellectual hierarchies within academia.

Finally, the author offers suggestions for achieving greater epistemological justice in the context of the framing and teaching of soft skills and emotional intelligence within higher education in ways that not only more equitably include Southern voices to promote dialogue with a wider diversity of indigenous knowledge systems, but which also incorporate evolving changes in the emerging digital world as well.

CHAPTER ONE

Who Gets to Decide What Qualifies as Emotional Intelligence?

When emotional intelligence comes to be discussed in many academic quarters of the Global North, students frequently encounter a seemingly obligatory lexicon where gentle expressions like ‘soft skills,’ ‘nurturing,’ ‘intangibles,’ ‘transformative,’ and ‘empowering’ carry the day (Jardim 2022). What all too often follows, it is my sad duty to report, perfunctorily converges into a pablum of wistful generalities about how academia ought to teach pupils to become more in touch with their innermost feelings so as to be nicer human beings—or at least less troublesome employees.

In a few cases, these philological generalities extend to imagine ways in which students might (perish the thought) speak their minds in such shrewd and subtle ways that they can more effortlessly gobble up whatever it is they desire whilst inflicting as little damage as possible to their intangible social credit scores.

But who really ought to decide what qualifies as emotional intelligence? And is a one-size-fits-all prescription something educators should be seeking after all?

In this brief paper, the author should like to share the perspective of students and scholars living in the Global South (Myanmar in this case), where proper soft skills and emotional intelligence may take on rather different dimensions.

CHAPTER TWO

Can We Unpack Pedagogical Oppression?

Positing an Asian perspective on soft skills (or anything else, for that matter) requires, to begin with, more than just a smidgeon of ethnocentric blindness. ‘Asia’ is, after all, arguably a geographic imaginary created long ago in Europe (Lawson 2021). Generally speaking, the concept of Asia provides a shorthand for what Western scholars charitably describe as just about everything directly connected to Europe, but which is not a part of the ruling centre (Mamadouh 2021).

Categorising, therefore, some 4.6 billion people, 49 nationalities, over 2,300 languages, nearly 5,000 self-described ethnic groups, about 30 major religions, and a wide range of political and economic systems (Lee 2020) into a single definable group necessarily becomes unwieldy. After all, how can we accurately make unified claims about such a diverse collection of peoples and cultures?

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That said, let us nevertheless acknowledge that differences are likely to exist between so-called Western and Eastern cultures (R'boul 2022)—and indeed, that those differences are likely to extend to soft-skills communication practises as we commonly know them (Kennedy 2022).

CHAPTER THREE What are Soft Skills in Asia?

We begin our inquiry in Myanmar where this author lives, wherein, as in many parts of Asia, one encounters a linguistic landscape that exudes obliqueness (Chung 2021); where what is not said often carries as much weight as the words which have actually been uttered (Irwin 2020).

This symbiosis reflects deeply rooted cultural values including self-restraint, harmony, and respect for authority. Indeed, the art of articulating dissent, to cite a particularly thorny example in Myanmar's case, requires more than a little finesse, as direct confrontation is normally viewed with disdain (Curato 2020).

Contrast this with the popular freewheeling forms of discourse so well honed in the West (Tanbir 2022), where a robust polemical tradition thrives, and dissenters are often celebrated as intellectual icons (Minozzi 2020).

In such settings Global Northern claims about the sanctity of individualism reign supreme (Nowak 2021), fostering environments where it is allowable to vigorously and publicly dissect arguments whilst listeners revel in the irreverence of the process (Garnham 2020).

The hierarchical structure inherent in many Asian societies on the other hand—Myanmar included—imbues a great many public conversations in the East with a palpable requirement of deference to authority (Bell 2020). Even today, an oration of Castroesque length by a respected elder in one's local village is apt to hold sway over the hearts and minds of young people, with dissenting voices relegated to the margins—in spite of our present age of social media and its attendant distractibility (Huard 2022).

Likewise, in countries like South Korea and Malaysia deference to seniority and age is often a significant factor in language choices (Nguyen 2023, Sanget 2022). Soft skills training in leadership, therefore, must account for these cultural norms by emphasizing respectful communication and deference to authority in much of Asia, even if doing so differs from more egalitarian practises in Western contexts (Deep 2020).

Moreover, the art of emotional control must be mastered from an early age, a testament perhaps the need for resilience forged in the crucible of historical calamities. Indeed, the ability to maintain both offline and online composure in the face of adversity is, in many parts of the world, as prized as intellectual acumen (Anguiano-Carrasco 2022).

In fact, what might be considered simply healthy assertion in one culture may well be perceived as aggression in another. For example, if I receive a gift in the United States from a friend

or colleague, I am obligated by the mores of polite society to open the gift immediately in the presence of the giver. I must then provide some perfunctory comments about why the gift is special to me, how it is timely, or useful, and so on. Any less of a performance, and I would be considered roguish (Stafford 2021).

But if I am offered a similar gift in Myanmar, I am obligated to push it to one side quietly and with apparent disinterest, rendering only the barest of eye contact, and certainly not expressing any verbal reaction. Likewise, the giver will say next to nothing when offering the donation. And the two of us will continue on in due course, both ignoring the wrapped parcel which sits off to one side untouched. All educated people in Myanmar know how to do this, as surely as grown up Americans know to make a proper fuss (Carstens 2020).

If, on the other hand, I were to open the gift publicly to examine it in the Golden Land, or to comment on the present's value in any way, I would be viewed at once as a repulsive glutton cursed with but the weakest powers of self-control (Maung 2020).

Correspondingly in Asian countries influenced by Confucian values, there is often an emphasis on maintaining emotional restraint and composure in public settings, rather than demonstrating one's emotions transparently (Huang 2024).

Neither system, I claim, is right. Neither is wrong. Neither set of soft skills is better than the other. But within one's own indigenous culture, only one set of behaviours will bear a claim to appropriateness.

This is because in Asia—the lens of this paper—the intellectual and social landscape is a complex protean tapestry, where tradition and modernity collide, creating thought-provoking paradoxes. Yet, to romanticize this intricacy would be folly. Rather, in the context of defining which soft skills we ought to teach, we must look unblinkingly at the culture in which they reside.

In a great many Asian societies, for example, collectivism is valued in the sense that the needs of the group frequently take precedence over individual desires (Lacko 2020). Contrastingly, Western cultures more often prioritize individual achievement and autonomy (Lomas 2023).

Indeed, so great is the difference that some Chinese scholars argue that highly individualistic societies such as those in the West are (in spite of Adam Smith's claim to the contrary) philosophically opposed to democracy (Li 2020). "I don't care what the majority wants. I only care what I want!" they say. Conversely, so-called collective societies are, by way of contrast, more likely to achieve true democratic outcomes (Zhang 2020).

(It is beyond the scope of this paper, I am relieved to inform the reader, to answer this last assertion fully.)

In Japan, where the author lived some 25 years, the concept of 'wa' or harmony is crucial in group settings as well. And decisions are often made through consensus-building rather than by battling each individual's opinions, hoping for a win (Rayhan 2023). Soft skills training at the university level must be prepared to incorporate such local cultural nuances to foster effective teamwork where it makes sense to do so.

Finally, policy makers would do well to remember that a great many Asian countries have endured the trauma of colonisation and unwanted wars which continue to shape their collective psyches and thus soft skills rule constructions (Cooper 2020).

Consider Vietnam, Cambodia, and Laos under French rule (De la Roche 2021). Or India, Malaysia, and Myanmar annexed to the British Empire (Bennett 2021). Recall Indonesia invaded by the Dutch (de Zwart 2022), and the Philippines in succession first by Spain then the United States (Skrabania 2020). And let us neither forget the sufferings in Korea and parts of China at the hands of the Greater East Asia Co-Prospersity Sphere project (Satoh 2020). Powerful experiences like these leave indelible impacts.

In Myanmar for example, after having endured 124 years of war crimes consisting of 61 years of unprovoked military attacks followed 63 years of colonisation—the longest and most expensive conflict in the history of the British Empire it is worth noting (Campbell 2022)—readers may forgive the locals for feeling a bit surprised each time they hear their brothers and sisters from the EU lecture them about 'human rights' (Gordon 2020).

Survival is more to the point, and Myanmar people consider strength, persistence, patience, and endurance skills worth developing to that end (Gomersall 2023). Correspondingly in Japan, the unlucky recipient of the world's only nuclear attack, the concept of 'gaman' or endurance is highly valued, in which individuals are expected to endure hardships without complaint (Fathi 2022).

Educators would do well to acknowledge the diverse interpretations of soft skills requirements—including forms of verbal and emotional resilience—then develop their curricula appropriately (Tang 2020).

By incorporating such diverse perspectives into educational planning, we can more effectively contextualize soft skills training into a useful cultural framework for Asian societies, thereby promoting a more inclusive and culturally sensitive approach to education and ultimately workplace success (Robledo-Ardila 2022).

CHAPTER FOUR

Should there be an International Language?

Call me old-fashioned if you will, but I have always taken the view that the goal of creating a universal linguistic code—let alone declaring one language or another 'the global' choice—to be as nonsensical as it is intellectually lazy (Duarte 2023).

In the mosaic of human discourse, the ascendancy of English, for example, (though handy for those of us who were born in the Anglosphere) too easily ignores important diversities found in alternate linguistic traditions that might otherwise enrich our understanding of the human condition and help us therefore find ways of improving it (Gul 2023). Consider, by way of example, the biases inherent in the application of English words within the current globalisation project:

Why, one might question for example, are Asians living in the West normally labelled 'immigrants' by media outlets, whilst their European counterparts residing in the East are granted the self-appointed moniker 'expats'? Is this anything more than an exercise in linguistic hegemony designed to perpetuate an unwarranted hierarchy of privilege and power (De Carvalho 2023)?

Likewise, examine if you will the semantic contortions used to label successful business leaders around the world, which also betray a systemic bias reeking of imperialism. In Myanmar, for example, nearly all wealthy businesspersons are vilified as 'cronies' in the English speaking press; while in Russia they are branded 'oligarchs' (Omeje 2021). But in America, this same category of businesspersons is generally lauded as 'entrepreneurs' (Allcorn 2023).

Yet do not all these groups engage in fairly similar practices of financial extraction and political patronage? If so, why do they require different designations?

And what can be said of the Orwellian doublespeak that resolutely defends public discourse on social media as vital to the interest of 'freedom of speech' in Global Northern countries whilst routinely denouncing similar patterns of engagement in the Global South as 'hate speech' which must be eliminated on the grounds of human rights (Tontodimamma 2021)?

Is this not also a sort of pungent hypocrisy underscoring the precariousness of linguistic absolutism?

And we dare not speak of the moral calculus that distinguishes 'murder' from 'collateral damage' in conflict zones of late, lest we expose the intentional elasticity of soft words in the service of geopolitical expediency. The death of innocents too easily serves as a triumphalist cliché when inflicted on one side, but a moral outrage when inflicted on another (Semerdjian 2024).

To suppress regional nuances in the articulation of soft skills, is therefore, I claim, to perpetuate a dangerous tyranny of linguistic hegemony, denying humanity the richness of its diverse intellectual heritage in solving shared problems (Stein-Smith 2021).

CHAPTER FIVE

Can We Tackle a New Set of Shared Problems Together?

Let us turn now to our present situation. Even as we consider these ideas together, a rising tide of new shared challenges appears gathering on the horizon, necessitating a collective re-

evaluation of our approach to nurturing intangible soft-skills competencies.

Consider first the impact of social media, that intoxicating elixir of connectivity that has metastasised into a breeding ground for intellectual mayhem (Azzaakiyyah 2023). Are not the incessant bombardment of carefully selected information and the relentless pursuit of validation through performative posting and commenting, along with the insidious erosion of attention spans symptoms of a miasmatic decay in human interaction (Boer 2020)?

In fairness, legacy media was before this, many scholars agree, largely an exercise in propaganda—though propaganda with fewer voices (Derman 2021).

But social media has morphed into a platform for maintaining states of perpetual outrage (Carpenter 2020), pigeonholing users into extreme group positions (Hiaeshutter-Rice 2022), distorting the traditional rules of logic (e.g., ‘whataboutism’) (Dykstra 2020), proliferating conspiracy theories (Cinelli 2022), creating an addiction to virtue signalling (Kamalath 2021), trolling (Ortiz 2020), edge-lord behaviours (Goldberg 2022), that ultimately culminates in an ad hoc one-strike-and-you’re-out cancel-culture in response to a growing number of conundrums (Gondringer 2021).

The result? A cacophony of voices drowning in a sea of circumlocution, where the distinction between genuine discourse and intellectual looting becomes increasingly blurred (Harambam 2020).

Nor let us delude ourselves into imagining the realm of soft skills is impervious to the encroaching tide of artificial intelligence. The rapidly evolving spectre of AI demands a substantial paradigm shift in our approach to intellectual inquiry (Adigüzel 2023). No longer can we rely solely on investigative prowess or literary appurtenance to navigate the labyrinth of information overload (Bates 2020).

Instead, we must embrace the ontological imperative of cultivating new forms of academic resilience, and new ways of interacting with our artificial friends, lest we succumb to yet another intellectual hypocrisy of our own making.

Even the proliferation of online Zoom meetings necessitates a re-examination of our interpersonal dynamics within the digital sphere (Wilbert 2023). With the rise of remote working, for example, universities must prepare students with more effective interpersonal communication skills through virtual teamwork exercises and cross-cultural sensitivity training (Popovici 2020).

The University of Hong Kong, for instance, offers virtual teamwork modules where students collaborate with peers from diverse cultural backgrounds, enhancing their communication skills in remote settings (Yang 2022). Similarly, Singapore Management University incorporates a holistic curriculum emphasizing collaborative learning and real-world projects whether virtual or live in class (Cheah 2022). These

approaches not only foster problem-solving and conflict resolution skills—both important components of soft skills training—but also promote leadership through experiential learning (Morozova 2022).

And let us not forget we are still in the infancy of digital education. It is yet unproven whether the world will settle on a preference for remote experiences, virtual reality, asynchronous collaboration, and the like. It is entirely possible some societies and some universities may snap back to a preference for live teaching to offer greater value after the digital honeymoon is over (Kulikowski 2022).

Ultimately, if universities offer remote classes (via Zoom, Teams, or whatever) as a means to connect with people whom they would not otherwise have been able to serve, then that is, of course, a wonderful thing. But if higher education simply offers remote learning experiences because students are lazy and want a faster, easier way to finish their degrees that requires less effort, or so that universities can make more money, then our efforts will likely fail over time (Hensley 2022).

The salient question of how to navigate the gendarme of soft skills and their convergence with our brave new online-offline world looms large. From the artless art of virtual eye contact to the subtle nuances of body language, the landscape of online interaction demands a level of self-awareness and adaptability hitherto unexplored (Aagaard 2022).

In the face of these emerging challenges, the imperative of reconsidering soft skills on a local level—including the creation of a new set of ‘indigenous digital soft skills’—becomes more evident with each passing day (Goulart 2022).

Only through concerted efforts in researching, hypothesising, testing, evaluating, then refining our shared definitions of soft skills within higher education will we be able to unleash the full potential of our intellectual arsenal so that we may emerge unscathed from the intellectual fire of the digital age.

The road ahead may be fraught with uncertainties, but so is it also pregnant with possibilities. And it is in the crucible of these new challenges that the irrefutable truths of our intellectual future will be forged (Bhargava 2021).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was funded by International Leadership University in Myanmar. Particular thanks are due to Bhavit Mehta who originated the topic for the Times Higher Education Asia Universities Summit 2024 in Kuala Lumpur, and to President Sibrandes Poppema of Sunway University for hosting the event. Also my gratitude to Professor Lim Weng Marc, Dean of Sunway Business School, for moderating the deeper discussion, and to Professor Jun Liu, Rector of City University of Macau, and Professor Yuko Harayama, Executive Director of RIKEN, for helping expertly unpack the modern roles soft skills plays in Asia at the Summit from a practical point of view.

Any mistakes are the author’s fault alone.

NO CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

ETHICS STATEMENT

This research was conducted with approval from the Research Ethics Committee of International Leadership University in Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar: Approval number 2024/2265157.

TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Dare, Richard (2024). Nurturing Soft Skills and Emotional Intelligence: A Particularly Asian Perspective. *International Journal of Decolonial Leadership*: 24 (1), 98-104. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11044608>

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